

Under the Blinding Light of Colonial Ideology: The (Re)formation of the Tiritiya Prakriti Social Group in Late Modern India

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Abstract

During the late eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, British linguists translated significant Sanskrit and Pali texts, laying the foundation for much of the legal system in colonial India. Notably, several nonbinary groups, which were collectively referred to as 'eunuchs', evolved to represent what is known as the *tritiya prakriti*, or India's third gender. Current scholarship addresses the *tritiya prakriti* through a cultural lens, distinguishing it from the institution of eunuchism. It then analyses this group's historical context, professional roles, sexuality, and unique gender traits, while drawing a comparative analysis with harem-bound eunuchs. The study argues that eunuchs were historically created for specific occupational roles and are unlikely predecessors of the contemporary *tritiya prakriti* community. However, the colonial disbandment of harems and the conducted censuses changed classifications from solely Muslim male eunuchs to identification based on occupation. While categorising the overall third gender groups into specific castes, these censuses then inadvertently established the status of a distinct social group that predates the contemporary *tritiya prakriti* community. By situating *tritiya prakriti* within the framework of eunuchism, current research lays the groundwork for further exploration into the history of third-gender communities in India, which may contribute to addressing contemporary challenges related to inclusion and gender equality.

Keywords: *Tritiya prakriti*; Eunuch; Colonial India; Hijra; Third gender

Introduction

The legacy of British political influence in India began in the mid-eighteenth century, initially with the rise of the East India Company and later with the British Crown, which assumed control of governance in 1858. Rising from the lessons of losing a colony in North America, the British aimed to establish a relationship defined by trade, where instead of imposing direct control, they implemented a strategy centred on managing and organising knowledge (Hodge 2007). Under this framework, British linguists engaged in extensive efforts to translate key Sanskrit and Pali texts, which ultimately served as a means of indirect rule over the local populace (ibid.). Meanwhile, the Indian colony was granted a degree of autonomy, allowing

local populations to participate in their governance (Willoughby and Fenwick 1919). Although the translation of texts played a foundational role in establishing colonial authority at first, there was a significant shift in approach following the 1857 Rebellion. The uprising prompted the British administration to move from subtle control to a more direct form of governance, characterised by increased regulation and the codification of imperial authority (Pati 2010). A key example of this transformation is the establishment of the institution of the third gender (eunuchism) and its integration into the evolving legal and social frameworks of colonial rule (Bhardwaj 2024).

Several instances of Hindu deities changing their gender, appearing in various forms at different times, or merging to create androgynous or hermaphroditic entities—such as Agni, Aravan, and Arjuna—indicate that the concept of nonbinary identity has been part of Indian history for centuries. A prominent theme related to the third gender intersects further with the ideas of emasculation and fertility, exemplified by the goddess Bahuchara Mata, or the worship of the lingam, where the original castration of Shiva signifies a pivotal event that gave rise to universal fertility (Sutradhar 2022). Material culture also suggests that the third gender was highly regarded in the periods preceding British colonisation. Artistic representations and sculptures from ancient temples, such as those in the Khajuraho temples of Madhya Pradesh, for instance, appear to celebrate gender and sexual diversity. Moreover, castrated individuals are mentioned in the sixteenth and seventeenth-century works 'Tuzuk-i-Jahangiri' and 'Ain-i-Akbari' (Chakarawarti 2024).

As the eighteenth-century influx of British individuals progressed, so did their own observations of the nonbinary groups. The earliest references, including 'the Hermaphrodite Mahmud' or 'bonmots people' can be traced back to the Persian text *The Seir Mutaqherin* (Gannon 2009). The nonbinary groups were also frequently referred to as 'eunuchs' (Balamurugan and Thirunavukkarasu 2018), a classification that remained prevalent until the end of the colonial period. The English translation of this term, however, derived from several Sanskrit terms, including; *tritiya prakriti*, *pandaka*, *napumsaka*, *kliba*, *shandha*, *kesava* and *varshadhara* (Zwilling 1992; Zwilling and Sweet 2000). While the interpretation hence may appear intricate, it is worth noting that a section of the *Naradasmriti* further breaks down *pandaka* into a range of categories of impotent men (Hiltebeitel 1980), which includes: *nisargashandha* (naturally impotent individuals); *vadhri* (men who have had their testes removed by a blade); *pakshashandha* (another variant of *shandha* that can approach a woman every half month); *abhishapadhu guro* (a man who lacks virility due to influence from a spiritual guide); *abhishapadhu rogad* (impotent due to illness); *abhishapadhu devarodhat* (impotent due to the wrath of a deity); *sevyā* (this category is left undefined);

irshyarpandasha (unproductive due to jealousy); *vatareta* (impotent because his semen is as light as air); *akshipto* (impotent because he spills his semen); *moghabijsha* (lacks strength in his semen); *shalino* (timorous individuals) and *anyapatīs* (impotent only with a woman other than his wife) (Zwilling 1992; Zwilling and Sweet 2000). Moreover, the *Samantapasadika* commentaries by Buddhaghosa, further list five subcategories of *pandaka*: *napumsaka* (congenitally impotent individuals); *usuyapandaka* (those who fulfil their sexual desires through voyeurism); *pakkhapandaka* (individuals who are impotent for fourteen days of the month); *assittapandaka* (those who engage in fellatio to satisfy their desires); and *opakkamikapandaka* or individuals who require special effort or artifice to achieve ejaculation (ibid.).

This way, for clarity, the present study adopts the term 'tritiya prakriti' (the third gender in Sanskrit; Aggarwal 2017), to encompass a spectrum of nonbinary identities. The approach aligns with contemporary interpretations of the Indian third gender, which include individuals designated male at birth who undergo a transgender transition, with or without castration (Agha 2002; Master and Santucci 2003). Additionally, the term 'eunuch' is specifically used to refer to castrated males who served in Islamic courts. The scholarship first reviews how British colonial ideology, for the purpose of governance, consolidated diverse nonbinary groups into an institution of eunuchism. It then discusses the differences between harem-bound eunuchs and the *tritiya prakriti* through the lenses of their histories, professional roles, sexualities and unique gender traits. The study argues that harem eunuchs were purposefully designated for particular roles and do not solely serve as a historical precursor to the modern *tritiya prakriti* (*hijra*) community.

The Formation of Eunuchism

In the imagination of colonial translators, the *tritiya prakriti* were defined by narratives rooted in various ancient texts, emphasising their exclusion from society (Hardgrove 2024). Pali literature such as the *Kullavagga*, the *Mahavagga*, sections of the *Vinaya Pitaka*, and the *Milindapanha* played a significant role in this portrayal (ibid.). *Dharmashastras* together with the *Mitakshara*, *Dayabhaga*, and *Vyavahara Mayukha* were also among the

Sanskrit documents viewed as reflective of the Indian social landscape that consequently uncovered the historical underpinnings of colonial law (Gannon 2009). For instance, British linguists had drawn parallels between the goddess Bahuchara, linked with gender transformation, and the deities Kali and Amba Bhavani, associated with a spectrum of negative traits (Forbes 1924[1856]), including the hidden elements of blood sacrifice, supernatural fertility, and emasculation (McDermott and Kripal 2003). As a result, the perceived immorality of Kali became intertwined with the worship of the Bahuchara, thereby providing a rationale for viewing the worship practices of the *tritiya prakriti* as criminalised (Gannon 2009). This negative portrayal has also extended to numerous other deities, including Apurna, Devi, Kamakhya, Parvati, Prakriti or Umbika (ibid.).

Other interpretations also suggested that the *tritiya prakriti* held a low social standing. For instance, in the *Manusmriti* and *Gautamasmriti*, the punishment for their deaths was relatively lenient (Gannon 2009). In the *Mahabharata*, the third gender was positioned beneath oilmen, who were themselves considered inferior to *mlecchas* and labelled as the ‘dirt of mankind’ (Syed 2019; Gannon 2009: 220). Because the *tritiya prakriti* were often viewed as morally and sexually inappropriate (Allen *et al.* 1979), Hinduism, in its connection to the *tritiya prakriti*, was also regarded as lacking in moral aesthetics. As a result, concepts of gender transformation, unnatural fertility, and castration- particularly the ritualistic sacrifice of a man's penis to bestow fertility upon others- evoked themes of blood, sacrifice, indecency, and criminality (ibid.).

The *tritiya prakriti* were hence often characterised as an established and inherent group that obscured various themes of gender, including masculinity and sexuality. They were frequently viewed with devaluation, seen as untrustworthy, sexually deviant, and generally to be avoided (Newport 2018). Consequently, the *tritiya prakriti* were associated with traits that deviated from traditional notions of colonial masculinity, such as being perceived as incapable of engaging in battle, unfit for governance, and tied to servitude (Mazumdar 2016). Because this social group was portrayed as both marginalised and diverging from established masculine standards, translators

simplified a range of its non-dominant sexual categories into a singular identity: that of the eunuch, an inadequate form of masculinity (Gannon 2009). The newly established institution of eunuchism now represented a distinct category of personhood, encompassing a specific class of individuals across various dimensions of social existence, including religious, sexual, legal, and economic realms (ibid.).

A lack of uniformity associated with the *tritiya prakriti* characteristics in the early nineteenth century meant an uneven perception of the group; some depicted them as castrated sodomites, while others showed a degree of tolerance, albeit through a moralistic lens (Dutta 2013). Although some colonial officials were cautious not to impose excessive restrictions on their rights, particularly when such limitations could hinder their means of livelihood, by the mid-nineteenth century, the *tritiya prakriti* came under stricter regulation (Hinchy 2017). By 1871, heightened anxiety regarding the governance of the *tritiya prakriti* was reflected in government-sponsored initiatives such as censuses and gazetteers aimed at categorising them (Assadi 2024). As the century progressed, the approach to addressing the so-called ‘issue of the *hijra*’ shifted toward extermination. The representation of these translated texts came under the authoritative scrutiny of the law, with constructed identities being defined by legal endorsement (ibid.). Ultimately, their definition revolved around exclusion, resulting in the treatment of ‘eunuchs’ as a social category subjected to mechanisms of containment and regulation (Wald 2024).

The ramifications of the colonial translations were hence considerable. Utilising Indigenous texts as the basis for legislation, particularly with Act 27 of 1871, commonly referred to as the ‘Eunuch Act’, compelled those without genitals to comply with the stipulations found in various Sanskrit and Pali writings (Hinchy 2022). The committee responsible for the law cited numerous court cases from the 1850s as the catalyst for addressing issues related to *tritiya prakriti*, making it clear that they were a social concern that warranted legislative intervention (Hinchy 2019). The Act rendered it illegal for the *tritiya prakriti* to serve as guardians for minors, to make gifts or wills, or to adopt sons, and it prohibited them from inheriting property

(Hinchy 2017). As the Act was integrated into Part II of the Criminal Tribes Act, *tritiya prakriti* were not only explicitly identified in the law as sodomites, child kidnappers, and cross-dressers but were also associated with criminal tribes and perpetuated the perception of them as a group predisposed to criminality (Ghosh 2022).

Precursors of the Hijra Community?

Colonial translators associated harem eunuchs, commonly referred to as *khoja* or *khwaja*, with *tritiya prakriti*, probably due to their practice of castration or impotence. A closer examination of these two nonbinary categories indeed can reveal the similarity but also the complexity within distinct gender traits, shaped by their history, professional roles, and sexuality. Many scholars argue that the origins of *tritiya prakriti* can be traced back to Hindu epics and mythological tales, suggesting that this group represents ‘one of the oldest spiritual orders on earth’ (Osborn 1994: 2), with a history spanning between 4,000 and 2,500 years (Baird 2001). Within the detailed occupational and caste taxonomies associated with eunuchism, *tritiya prakriti* took on various roles as entertainers, wedding singers and dancers, cooks, fortune tellers, and mendicants (Hossain *et al.* 2022). Marco Polo also noted Hindu teachers in Bengal who ‘instruct on the principles of their idolatrous religion and necromancy whose doctrine prevails among all ranks, including the nobles and chiefs of the country’ (Polo and Charney 2004: 98). In Campbell’s Gazetteer of the Bombay Presidency, Faridi (1899) suggested that the primary reasons for making vows to the goddess Bahachara were infertility and illness, noting that the group was often known for engaging in sodomy, rudeness, and the use of alcohol and drugs, which contributed to their reputation for immorality.

Eunuchs, on the other hand, are associated with Islam, where there is a common belief that Muslims were responsible for the introduction of castration as a practice (Sweet and Zwilling 1993). This raises the strong possibility that eunuchs were largely absent in many regions until the arrival of Muslims (Edwardes 1960; Sweet and Zwilling 1993), indicating that the history of harem eunuchs is comparatively shorter. Eunuchs also played prominent roles as messengers, governors, and military leaders, and were responsible for raising royal sons in the *zenana* (women’s

quarters; Lal 2017). They were, in addition, associated with distinct psychological traits, including loyalty and faithfulness (Lal 2017), and were seen as passive victims in contrast to the *tritiya prakriti*, who were implicated in the abduction of children for the purpose of castration (Gannon 2009). Early authors such as Ebden (1855) and Chevers (1870) [1854] also characterised eunuchs as exhibiting effeminate traits and lacking traditional masculine characteristics. The absence of masculinity, linked to their castration, was not necessarily reflected among the *tritiya prakriti* (Gannon 2009). Moreover, the harem-bound eunuchs generally adopted men’s clothing in contrast to the *tritiya prakriti* that, from the late seventeenth to the early nineteenth centuries, were often depicted wearing a combination of male and female clothing, or donning women’s attire later in the eighteenth century (*ibid.*).

While eunuchs were commonly recognised as impotent men, further, census enumerators revealed that the *tritiya prakriti* included both men and women. In Bombay, for example, out of 47 recorded *tritiya prakriti*, 34 were male and 11 were female (Gannon 2009). In Punjab, the figures were even more pronounced. With 631 individuals identified as *tritiya prakriti*, 547 were men and 84 were women (*ibid.*). In addition, Baillie’s (1798) observations supported the conclusions drawn by Drew (1892) regarding the marital status of individuals identified as *tritiya prakriti*. Some male *tritiya prakriti* were wed to non-*tritiya prakriti* women, while some female *tritiya prakriti* were married to men who do not identify as *tritiya prakriti* (Gannon 2009). Additionally, an 1843 article in *The Lancet* noted that *tritiya prakriti* assisted male eunuchs in guarding women who were often part of Muslim harems, while Hindu society institutionalised female eunuchs within their own harems (*ibid.*).

Following the British disbandment of harems, however, eunuchs transitioned to street life, taking with them the skills they had honed within the sultanate courts (Gannon 2009), contributing to the complexities surrounding religious and gender categories. In Rajputana, a princely state where the British conducted the census, Abbott (1892), for instance, recorded that out of a total of 356 *tritiya prakriti*, 167 were Muslim, 186 were Hindu or Jain, and three were identified as Animists. In 1901, the Gazetteer of the Bombay Presidency published

an article by Kirparam Bhimbhai asserting that *tritiya prakriti* are eunuchs from either Islamic or Hindu traditions, devoted to the goddess Bahucharaji. Notably, despite their shared devotion, members of these different faiths maintained separation during communal dining (Gannon 2009).

This way, referring to all nonbinary groups in colonial accounts as ‘eunuchs’ would have led to the effective erasure of the *tritiya prakriti* from historical discourse. The 1881 censuses, however, marked a significant shift in this classification, moving from identifying *tritiya prakriti* solely as Muslim male eunuchs to defining the individuals based on their occupational roles (ibid.). Baillie (1894), for instance, categorised them into nine sub-castes, while Maclagan (1892) identified eleven sub-castes within one group. Moreover, the *tritiya prakriti* from various religious backgrounds were assigned different titles (ibid.). By delineating the *tritiya prakriti* into specific castes, reflecting the British perception of Indian social hierarchy, these censuses (inadvertently) solidified their status as a distinct social group. Colonial institutions, particularly legal frameworks, have, therefore, leveraged the classifications to define the *tritiya prakriti* as ‘other’ (Gannon 2009). In this way, by emphasising their specific characteristics, these colonial narratives established the foundational conditions for academic interpretations of the *tritiya prakriti*, creating a conceptual framework that underpinned much of the modern scholarly research conducted on this group.

Conclusions

In summary, the *tritiya prakriti* have been defined by the censuses as marginalised and criminalised rather than being represented from a cultural perspective. The translation of legally and socially significant Indian texts into English was influenced by an interpretative framework that shaped the understanding of this group. The framework portrayed them as a repository of social significance, and in conjunction with the colonial context, contributed to the formation of a distinct social group. Colonialism hence established a

dualistic perspective on gender, along with notions of deviance and criminality directed at gender-diverse communities. These stigmatising beliefs have since been entrenched within legal frameworks and have influenced Indian cultural practices in general, and contemporary *tritiya prakriti* in particular. Consequently, they have been facing systemic discrimination and marginalisation, with limited support available in educational, medical, social, and policy domains. It has taken over a hundred years to dismantle certain aspects of colonial laws, necessitating political efforts from various stakeholders, and the consequences are evident.

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